

Proximal sensing for CREDIBLE carbon farming: case studies, the related digital ecosystem and technological uptake

D3.2

<https://zenodo.org/records/20393825>

Project CREDIBLE: “Building momentum and trust to achieve credible soil carbon farming in the EU”.

Funded by the European Union under the Grant Agreement n° 101112951.

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CREDIBLE
EU carbon farming

Document information

GRANT AGREEMENT N°	101112951
Project title	Building momentum and trust to achieve credible soil carbon farming in the EU
Project acronym	CREDIBLE
Project duration	36 months
Coordinators	SAE
Related work packages(s)	WP3
Related task(s)	T3.2
Lead organisation	University of Helsinki
Contributing partner(s)	UFZ, CREA, COOP, UCSC, BEC
Due date	31/01/2026
Submission date	30/01/2026
Dissemination level	Public (PU)

History

Version	Date	Author	Description	Reviewed by
1.0	30/4/25	Rajewicz, P.	First draft ready for review	Atherton, J.
2.0	21/8/25	Fernandez, P.; Knitsch, V.; Piccini, C.; Rajewicz, P.; Sagarna, J.; Tziachris, P.	Second draft ready for review	Atherton, J.
3.0	30/9/25	Editorial: Rajewicz, P.; Atherton, J.	Third draft ready for review	Focus Group 3.2
4.0	30/10/25	Editorial: Rajewicz, P.; Atherton, J.	Deliverable ready for official internal review process	Atherton, J.; Rajewicz, P.
5.0	12/11/25	Editorial: Rajewicz, P.; Atherton, J.	Deliverable internally reviewed	Werban, U., Bullova, T.
6.0	10/12/25	Editorial: Rajewicz, P.; Atherton, J.	Last corrections, deliverable submitted	Atherton, J.; Rajewicz, P.

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Executive summary

Purpose: The purpose of this document is to report on the potential of proximal sensing in Monitoring, Reporting and Verification (MRV) systems for carbon farming, considering currently available and emerging technologies. It also examines the associated digital tools that support proximal sensing use and the social uptake of the evolving technologies, aiming to identify key opportunities, challenges, and recommendations for their effective implementation across Europe. By demonstrating the practical applications, benefits, and challenges of proximal sensing with real-world cases, the report aims to provide stakeholders with actionable insights on how to enhance the credibility, efficiency, and scalability of carbon farming initiatives across Europe.

Intended audience: This report is intended for policymakers, land users, and other stakeholders involved in carbon farming, soil management, and agricultural land-use planning. It is relevant for decision-makers at the EU and national levels, practitioners interested in MRV systems, and organizations looking to adopt or support proximal sensing technologies in monitoring sustainable carbon sequestration initiatives. By highlighting practical case studies and demonstrating the integration of proximal sensing with digital tools and societal considerations, the report provides information of direct relevance to all groups seeking to implement, regulate, or benefit from carbon farming practices. Note that the report is not intended for expert practitioners and does not contain detailed measurement or sampling protocols for field sensing.

Description of the main activities: The report summarises activities carried out under project CREDIBLE Task 3.2, including an expert survey and evaluation of proximal sensing technologies for soil organic carbon monitoring, as well as gathering information on market-ready solutions. A focus group was formed to help identify key benefits and challenges associated with integrating proximal sensing into MRV systems for carbon farming. Engagement with academic researchers, private providers, public cooperatives, and various stakeholders ensured a broad understanding of the technological, operational, and societal dimensions of proximal sensing adoption.

In addition, by positioning proximal sensing within the broader digital MRV ecosystem, the scope of the report was broadened to include data management, interoperability, and near real-time monitoring possibilities (Section 4). Social aspects, such as farmer acceptance, skill requirements, and trust in digital solutions, were highlighted to provide recommendations for equitable, scalable adoption (Section 5). Real-life company case

studies and network engagement (Section 3) formed the foundation for demonstrating practical pathways for deploying proximal sensing in carbon farming MRV systems.

Key results:

- **Benefits:** Proximal sensing technologies offer cost-effective, scalable, and high-frequency monitoring of soil organic carbon (SOC), which can significantly reduce operational costs while maintaining reliable data quality.
- **Methodological insights:** A good-but-not-perfect methodological framework can accelerate the adoption of proximal sensing-based MRV. Overly restrictive guidelines, particularly around bulk density measurement, may hinder innovation, suggesting a need for flexible, peer-reviewed benchmarking methodologies.
- **Innovation priorities:** Increased funding for research and innovation in proximal sensing technologies, including a push towards open-source data libraries, is essential to support the continued adoption of technology.
- **Regulatory and digital framework gaps:** Regulatory frameworks that support digitalization, data interoperability, GDPR-compliant data ownership, and digital literacy for farmers are critical to reduce uncertainty, lower MRV costs, and foster trust in proximal sensing-based MRV.
- **Farmer adoption:** Incentive mechanisms that align with farmers' economic realities—such as shared-service models, financial support, training, and peer-led demonstrations—are key to scaling adoption while ensuring equitable access and credible carbon sequestration claims.

Research and practice implications: The findings emphasize that proximal sensing is complementary to traditional laboratory and remote sensing MRV technologies, offering practical benefits for large-scale and repeated monitoring of SOC due to its low relative cost and firm anchoring in the digital ecosystem. Enhanced adoption requires the prioritization of flexible methodological frameworks, supporting digital infrastructure, fostering farmer engagement, and promoting accessible training.

Policy implications: Policymakers should consider explicitly integrating proximal sensing technologies into MRV methodologies, ensuring that regulatory frameworks accommodate digital solutions, incentivize adoption, and provide financial and training support for land users. Alignment with EU funding priorities and standards for digitalization will strengthen the credibility and scalability of carbon farming initiatives while contributing to climate and soil health objectives.

Conclusion: Proximal sensing technologies have significant potential to enhance MRV for carbon farming across Europe, principally by lowering measurement costs. By identifying practical benefits, challenges, and providing recommendations, the report supports stakeholders in making informed decisions, guiding policy development, and promoting the scalable, credible adoption of proximal sensing in carbon farming initiatives.

List of acronyms and abbreviations

BD: Bulk density

CAP: Common Agricultural Policy

CF: Carbon farming

CRCF: Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming

EC: European Commission

EU: European Union

FMIS: Farm Management Information Systems

GDPR: General Data Protection Regulation

LUCAS: Land Use/Cover Area Frame Survey

ML: Machine learning

MRV: Monitoring, Reporting and Verification

SOC: Soil organic carbon

Vis, NIR, MIR: Visible (400–700nm), near-infrared (700–2,500 nm), mid-infrared (2,500–25,000 nm)

1. Project summary

This deliverable is part of the EU-funded project under the topic HORIZON-MISS-2022-SOIL-01-06, titled: Building momentum and trust to achieve credible soil carbon farming in the EU (project acronym: CREDIBLE, Grant Agreement #101112951).

The main goal of the CREDIBLE project is to build momentum and trust for the implementation of carbon farming in the EU. This will be primarily achieved by setting up and moderating a network of initiatives/projects/stakeholders for favouring transparency, environmental integrity, and methodology standardisation in soil carbon accounting. Such a network will be responsible for pushing forward multiple discussions (articulated around three main themes: which practices; what standards; how to monitor) and is expected to evolve from a mostly technical/scientific network at the onset of the project, into a process catalysing policy making and business innovation toward its end. The transparent, open access, multi actor dialogues required to build trust and co-create solutions will be orchestrated around three annual European Carbon Farming Summits, which will present opportunities for the network to interact with the broader stakeholder community and grow to the point it would attract further fundings for long term sustainability. Through the action, four specific objectives (SO) will be achieved:

SO1) to build and disseminate a practical toolbox for promoting carbon farming, capable of taking into account local land uses, best practices, and multi-actor interests;

SO2) to identify options for benchmarking and selecting standards, certification mechanisms, and policy instruments for carbon farming;

SO3) to favour the establishment of a network of soil carbon data collectors and repositories to improve measuring and monitoring carbon dynamics;

SO4) to build up processes and tools to drive conversations for the upscaling of carbon farming. CREDIBLE's ambition is to support the European Commission and the Expert Group on Carbon Removal in the identification and upscale of solutions for soil carbon farming. Tables 1 and 2 provide further information on the structure and composition of the project.

Table 1 - CREDIBLE's work package structure.

WP#	WP Name	Lead
WP1	Practical knowledge and fit-for-region blueprint for carbon scheme development	11-BSAG
WP2	Navigating and selecting carbon standards and policy instruments	12-EEB
WP3	Existing monitoring capabilities as enablers of soil data collection and sharing	8 - UFZ
WP4	Networking and communication actions to drive Carbon Farming in the EU	15-CKIC
WP5	Project management and coordination	1 – SAE

Table 2 - CREDIBLE's consortium composition.

Participant organisation name	Short name	Country
Soluciones Agrícolas Ecoinnovadoras SL	SAE	ES
Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore	UCSC	IT
European Conservation Agriculture Federation	ECAF	BE
Association des Chambres d'Agriculture de l'Arc Atlantique	AC3A	FR
Greifswald University	UG	DE
Ecologic Institute	ECO	DE
European Association of Remote Sensing Companies	EARSC	BE
Helmholtz-Zentrum für Umweltforschung GmbH	UFZ	DE
Centre de Recerca Ecològica i Aplicacions Forestals	CreAF	ES
Cooperativas Agro-alimentarias de España U de coop sociedad cooperativa	COOP	ES
Baltic sea action group	BSAG	FI
European Environmental Bureau	EEB	BE
European agroforestry federation	EURAF	FR
BioEconomy Cluster	BEC	SK
Climate KIC Foundation	CKIC	NL
University of Helsinki	UH	FI

Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food	ILVO	BE
Consiglio per la ricerca in agricoltura e l'analisi dell'economia agraria	CREA	IT
Agricultural Applications Private Company (AgroApps)	APPS	GR
Institute for Climate Economics	I4CE	FR
Ellinikos Georgikos Organismos - DIMITRA	ELGO	GR

2. Introduction

2.1 Introduction to carbon farming in EU policy

Carbon farming is a set of climate-friendly agricultural practices that mitigate carbon loss from soils and vegetation through land management strategies. It plays a pivotal role in climate change mitigation, as enhanced soil carbon sequestration contributes to lowering atmospheric CO₂ levels, improving soil health and biodiversity, and promotes sustainable agriculture. Specific carbon farming practices include cover cropping, no-till farming, agroforestry, and rotational grazing.

Within the European Union (EU), carbon farming is increasingly prioritized in response to the European [Green Deal](#) (2019) and, within the Farm to Fork Strategy, as part of the ambition of making Europe the first climate-neutral continent by 2050. The Fit for 55 package, part of the [EU's Climate Law](#) (2021), also targets reducing net greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions by 55% by 2030. This framework has put carbon farming at the centre of EU policies, developing incentive schemes aimed at supporting farmers in adopting carbon farming practices while ensuring that such initiatives are scientifically robust, economically viable, and environmentally sustainable. Effective implementation of carbon farming in the EU relies heavily on robust **Monitoring, Reporting, and Verification (MRV)** systems to track and validate the carbon sequestration efforts of farmers and land managers.

MRV and carbon farming policy in the EU

A major challenge in carbon farming lies in accurately and cost-effectively monitoring soil organic carbon (SOC) stocks at both the field and landscape levels. The EU policies, especially through the [Common Agricultural Policy](#) - CAP (2025), emphasize the need for MRV systems that can reliably measure carbon sequestration outcomes ([Sustainable carbon cycles – Carbon farming](#), 2021). MRV ensures that carbon sequestration practices are transparent, measurable, and credible, forming the basis for issuing carbon credits and accessing climate-related subsidies or incentives. Such MRV systems are essential for linking carbon farming practices to carbon credits in voluntary and anticipated regulated carbon markets, as well as ensuring compliance with EU sustainability goals. The European Commission (EC) has recognized the need for standardized MRV frameworks as part of its 2023 [proposal for a Carbon Removal Certification Framework](#), which aims to harmonize methodologies across Member States (2023). By establishing clear guidelines for quantifying carbon removals and ensuring

environmental integrity, the EU's policy approach seeks to build trust among stakeholders and enable a scalable, science-based carbon farming market.

The European Union's **CRCF Regulation** ([EU/2024/3012](#), 2024) was published in the Official Journal on 6 December 2024 and entered into force on 26 December 2024. This regulation establishes the first EU-wide voluntary certification system for carbon removals, carbon farming, and carbon storage in products, aiming to enhance transparency and environmental integrity in these activities. Since its adoption, the European Commission has been working on developing detailed methodologies for certifying various carbon removal activities. These methodologies are being refined through expert group meetings and public consultations, with the goal of finalizing them to ensure they meet the established quality criteria. Looking ahead, the Commission is expected to implement purchasing programs to stimulate demand for certified carbon removals.

2.2 The potential of proximal sensing in MRV: digitalization and social uptake in EU carbon farming

Proximal sensing technologies, which include measuring devices like soil sensors, portable spectrometers, and geophysical probes, used within close proximity to the soil, are increasingly recognized as a valuable tool in the context of EU climate and agricultural policy. Proximal sensing is directly or indirectly referenced in key EU policies, including the [European Soil Strategy and the Carbon Farming Initiative](#) (2021), as part of an integrated approach to improve MRV systems. Proximal sensing technologies are viewed as a potential solution to improve data collection, enhancing the accuracy, cost-efficiency, and resolution of SOC estimates, and supporting large-scale monitoring efforts.

Because they are on-site and rapid, proximal sensing technologies reduce the reliance on more expensive and time-consuming off-site laboratory analyses. This is particularly relevant for carbon farming, where reliable quantification of carbon sequestration is based on robust sampling schemes, i.e., repeated spatial measurements. These are then fed into models or compared with baselines that are essential for verifying emission reductions, issuing carbon credits, and maintaining environmental integrity. Furthermore, as these technologies often do more than just estimate carbon, as they help support the EU's broader sustainability objectives by contributing to soil health monitoring, precision agriculture, and adaptive land management practices.

As the EU moves forward with the further development of CRCF ([EU/2024/3012](#), 2024), integrating proximal sensing into standardized MRV protocols could play a key role in scaling up carbon farming practices and ensuring their alignment with the Union’s climate neutrality targets and biodiversity goals.

Figure 1: Overview of key components of the report: spectroscopy-based soil measurements, on-farm sensor deployment, data digitalization for SOC estimation, and the role of social uptake in technology adoption.

In this report, we examine the potential of proximal sensing technologies to complement existing MRV approaches in carbon farming. The report combines technological assessment, real-world case studies, and stakeholder insights to outline practical pathways for implementation (Section 3). It also explores how digitalization (Section 4) and social factors (Section 5) influence adoption and concludes with targeted recommendations to inform future EU policies (Section 6).

3. Proximal sensing

3.1 What is proximal sensing?

A wide array of proximal sensing techniques is currently available or under development, each with specific strengths depending on the target soil property. Among the most widely researched and applied methods are visible and near-infrared (Vis-NIR) spectroscopy, gamma-ray spectroscopy, laser-induced breakdown spectroscopy (LIBS), electrical conductivity sensors, and inelastic neutron scattering (INS). By enabling detailed and high-throughput assessment of key soil characteristics, these technologies are poised to transform SOC monitoring practices. In particular, they offer significant potential for improving MRV frameworks in carbon farming by addressing key challenges such as spatial heterogeneity, cost-efficiency, and temporal coverage. In summary, proximal sensing represents a critical technological advance in pursuit of accurate, cost-effective, and scalable (i.e. applicable across large or multiple areas and differing sites, regions, or contexts, e.g., to different soil types) soil monitoring systems. Its integration into carbon farming strategies can play a pivotal role in supporting the EU's broader climate and agricultural objectives, including those set out in the [Green Deal](#) (2019), the [European Soil Strategy](#) (2021), and the proposed [CRCF](#) (2024).

Proximal sensing within the measurement technology ecosystem

A range of technologies is currently employed in MRV that complement traditional soil sampling, including remote sensing, robotics, and automated sensing technologies (e.g., drones). Each technology has strengths and weaknesses and a different role to play in a combined MRV system.

As carbon farming scales up across diverse agricultural landscapes in Europe, the integration of proximal sensing into MRV frameworks, as demonstrated by the emergence of commercial offerings/interviews (see *Section 3.5*), could enhance the credibility and transparency of carbon sequestration claims, support the certification of carbon credits, and ultimately contribute to achieving the EU's climate and soil health targets.

Remote sensing technologies, such as satellite imagery, are commonly used to monitor above-ground vegetation, track land-use changes over large geographic areas, and estimate above-ground biomass. These methods are highly effective in providing large-scale coverage and are particularly useful for observing vegetation dynamics, early warning systems, and land management strategies. However, they are largely limited to surface-level observations and struggle to capture below-ground processes, such as SOC accumulation. An additional limitation occurs in heterogeneous landscapes, where variations in soil composition and moisture content further reduce the accuracy of remote assessments.

Robotics and automated sensing platforms, such as drones equipped with high-resolution cameras and multispectral or thermal sensors have emerged as a flexible, cost-effective complement to satellite-based monitoring of vegetation cover and land-use practices. They offer detailed imagery at the field level, enabling vegetation productivity monitoring, land-use changes, and certain surface indicators of soil health. Tractor or robot-borne sensors, which are not really distinct from proximal sensing, also offer good potential for close to ground or sub-surface sampling.

In short:

- large-scale coverage (satellites)
- flexible for vegetation/land-use (drones)
- cost-efficient for surface-level data
- incompetent for below-ground SOC
- inconsistent integration with field data

Proximal sensing technologies are diverse and include portable instruments and sensors that measure samples from close to or under the surface. Technologies include visible and near-infrared (Vis-NIR) spectrometers, and electromagnetic sensors (see also *Table* on page 18), which can be deployed directly in the field to obtain higher spatial resolution of SOC measurements directly from the field, addressing the issue of variability within different plots of land. Unlike remote methods, proximal sensing provides a closer connection with the soil, for example, some systems probe within the soil.

In short:

- field-deployed
- high-resolution, localized SOC data
- more cost-effective than repeated lab sampling
- greater uncertainty compared to traditional soil sampling

Traditional soil sampling and laboratory analyses remain the gold standard for SOC measurement, providing highly accurate, ground-truth data. These methods involve collecting physical soil samples in the field and analysing them in the lab for carbon content, typically using combustion or spectroscopic techniques. Despite its accuracy, this approach is resource-intensive, requiring significant time, labour, and financial investment. The need for repeated sampling to ensure accuracy increases the cost and reduces the feasibility for widespread, ongoing use in large-scale carbon farming operations.

In short:

- highly accurate
- provides ground-truth SOC data
- costly, labour-intensive, time-consuming
- limited scalability for large-scale carbon farming

Benefits of proximal sensing for carbon farming MRV

Proximal sensing technologies offer several significant advantages for improving MRV systems in the context of carbon farming. One of their primary benefits is the possibility for repeated, spatially explicit measurements of SOC. This level of detail is particularly important in agricultural fields where soil properties can vary significantly over short distances. Fine-resolution data provide farmers and stakeholders with timely insights into carbon dynamics e.g., over a project lifetime, which are critical for tailoring land management practices to site-specific conditions, thereby enhancing the effectiveness of carbon sequestration strategies. Additionally, proximal sensing technologies enable real-time monitoring, generating data more frequently than traditional soil sampling methods. Unlike traditional laboratory-based soil sampling—which involves delays due to sample transport, processing, and analysis—proximal sensors can generate continuous or high-frequency data directly in the field. This temporal immediacy allows farmers and land managers to quickly respond to changing soil conditions or to verify the impact of specific practices on SOC dynamics (Stenberg et al., 2010; Grunwald, 2016).

Another key advantage is cost-effectiveness. Undoubtedly, the initial investments in hardware and calibration may be required, but so-called “cooperatives” (e.g., [Agri-food Cooperatives of Spain](#)) can be used as a “tool” for farmers to decrease this potential starting barrier, as the investment would be equally shared among all members (see more in Section 4.3). Then, the proximal sensing technologies can significantly reduce the need for repeated manual soil sampling, laboratory analysis, and field labour over time. Studies have shown that portable spectrometers and geophysical sensors can perform rapid assessments at a fraction of the long-term cost of traditional methods, often reducing recurring expenses by 2–5 times (Adamchuk et al., 2004; Sudduth et al., 2010). Additionally, on-site platforms or vehicle-mounted sensors, balance the accuracy of the data with high speed and lower costs. This makes proximal sensing particularly suitable for scaling up carbon monitoring efforts across large agricultural landscapes and for enabling participation of smaller or resource-limited farms in carbon credit schemes. Furthermore, proximal sensors are adaptable to different soil types and conditions, provided they are properly calibrated, making them versatile tools for various landscapes and agricultural systems (Stenberg et al., 2010; Kuang and Mouazen, 2011). Proximal sensors, calibrated and validated with laboratory and field reference data and standardized protocols, can provide consistent and repeatable measurements across different farming systems, including arable land, grassland, and agroforestry settings, provided that sensor performance is regularly benchmarked, as long-term stability over many years cannot be assumed.

Challenges of proximal sensing in carbon farming MRV

Despite its significant potential, proximal sensing technologies face several challenges that must be addressed to fully harness their benefits within MRV systems for carbon farming. One of the primary limitations is the need for robust calibration. Proximal sensors, especially those relying on spectral or geophysical principles (e.g. Vis-NIR spectroscopy or electromagnetic induction), must be calibrated against traditional laboratory-based measurements of SOC to ensure their accuracy and reliability (Stenberg et al., 2010). This calibration process involves developing prediction models using a set of reference samples analysed in the laboratory, which can be resource-intensive and site-specific. The need for frequent recalibration—due to variations in soil composition, moisture content, and management practices—adds further complexity to sensor deployment and limits their plug-and-play applicability (Viscarra Rossel et al., 2011). All this means that proximal sensing systems are ultimately built on laboratory measurements, which have their own uncertainties and nuances.

Another important challenge relates to the performance variability across different soil types and conditions. Certain proximal sensing technologies tend to perform less effectively in soils with high clay content, salinity, or water saturation, where signal interference or attenuation can occur (Kuang and Mouazen, 2011). For example, wet soils can significantly alter the spectral reflectance patterns measured by optical sensors, while high clay content may affect the conductivity readings of electromagnetic sensors. Managing this variability often requires the use of site-specific calibration models or correction algorithms, which may not always be straightforward to implement in large or heterogeneous landscapes (Grunwald, 2016).

A further complication arises from the volume and complexity of the data generated by proximal sensing systems. High-resolution, continuous data collection, while valuable, can produce vast datasets that require substantial computational resources, storage capacity, and advanced data processing algorithms. Interpreting this data in a meaningful way often involves machine learning techniques or multivariate statistical models, which demand specialized expertise and robust infrastructure. Without these capabilities, the sheer volume of raw sensor data can overwhelm users and reduce the practical utility of the technology in operational MRV contexts (Ramcharan et al., 2018). Here again, the “cooperatives” often can provide agronomic services to deal with the specialized expertise and infrastructure demand, such as data interpretation, sensor calibration guidance, and recommendations for soil management practices.

These challenges highlight the need for continued methodological development, including standardization of calibration protocols, improved sensor-soil interaction models, and integrated digital platforms capable of managing and interpreting complex data streams. Furthermore, to ensure wide adoption, there is a need to translate technical advances into user-friendly, field-deployable tools that can be used reliably by farmers, consultants, and carbon project developers. In this context, while fully transparent standardized protocols may be difficult to implement as more companies provide sensors or services, establishing benchmarking sites could offer a practical solution. Identifying one or more benchmark locations that cover a representative range of SOC—such as long-term trial experiments—would allow proximal sensing systems suppliers to demonstrate the reliability of their sensors.

3.2 Technologies survey

Proximal sensing encompasses a range of technologies that offer high-resolution, field-level data on soil properties, including SOC. Each of the considered technologies operates differently, providing unique insights into soil composition, structure, and carbon content. In the *Table* (page 18), some of the main proximal sensing technologies are explored in detail, explaining how they work and their relevance to carbon farming.

The table is based on the results of questionnaires (conducted in 2024 and 2025), which aimed to collect information and opinions on the most commonly used proximal sensing techniques through a straightforward evaluation. The questionnaire was distributed among members of the Focus Group: academics (including, but not limited to, those involved in soil research) and private sector representatives (technology and software developers working in carbon reporting, accounting, or certification). It was provided as an online questionnaire with questions on a scale of 1 to 5, for example: “*Accuracy: On a scale from 1 (least accurate) to 5 (most accurate), how would you rate the accuracy of Laser-Induced Breakdown Spectroscopy?*”. Please note that a deeper dive into the most popular, scalable, cost-effective, and relevant technologies—as highlighted by the results of the *Table* “*Evaluation summary of proximal sensing technologies in carbon farming*”—is provided in *Sections 3.3 and 3.4*.

EVALUATION SUMMARY OF PROXIMAL SENSING TECHNOLOGIES IN CARBON FARMING

CONVENTIONAL LAB ANALYSES

Conventional lab-based analyses refer to traditional and most widely accepted approach for determining soil organic carbon (SOC) levels. They involve physically collecting soil samples, transporting them to a lab, and using chemical reactions, e.g. combustion, to break down the soil and isolate organic carbon. The Walkley-Black method is one of the most well-known techniques used for this purpose. Due to its detailed chemical processes, this method provides highly accurate results and is often considered the gold standard for SOC measurements. However, it is time-consuming, labor-intensive, and expensive, limiting its use for large-scale or frequent monitoring. Despite these drawbacks, it remains the benchmark for calibration and validation of other SOC measurement techniques.

VIS-NIR-MIR SPECTROSCOPY

Spectroscopy-based methods, such as visible (VIS), near-infrared (NIR), and mid-infrared (MIR) spectroscopy, measure soil properties by analyzing how light reflects off soil samples. These techniques are non-destructive and can rapidly estimate SOC content. In general, MIR provides higher accuracy compared to VIS and NIR, especially in more complex soils. The method requires a good calibration model to ensure accuracy, which involves comparing spectroscopy data to a reliable reference, such as lab chemistry results. Once calibration is in place, spectroscopy becomes a fast and cost-effective tool for large-scale SOC monitoring, offering portability and the ability to cover large areas.

GAMMA-RAY SPECTROSCOPY

Gamma-ray spectroscopy (GRS) measures the natural gamma radiation emitted by soils, providing indirect information on soil properties like bulk density, texture, and moisture content. While not as precise for directly measuring SOC, gamma-ray spectroscopy can offer useful correlations with SOC in some cases. Its strength lies in its ability to rapidly assess large areas with minimal disturbance to the soil. This method is often integrated into soil monitoring systems that require broad-scale field assessments, such as land-use mapping or soil health evaluations. Its high scalability makes it a valuable tool for landscape-level assessments, although the equipment can be expensive and its ability to characterize deeper soils is limited.

LASER-INDUCED BREAKDOWN SPECTROSCOPY

LIBS - Laser-Induced Breakdown Spectroscopy uses a high-intensity laser to vaporize small amounts of soil material, and the resulting plasma emission is analyzed to determine elemental carbon content, including SOC. This technique is highly accurate and can be performed in the field, making it an attractive option for direct, on-site SOC measurements. LIBS is also relatively fast compared to conventional methods and offers high portability. However, it requires careful calibration to ensure precision, and the specialized equipment can be costly. Despite these challenges, LIBS is one of the more accurate field-deployable technologies for SOC analysis, offering a balance between accuracy and convenience.

ELECTRICAL CONDUCTIVITY SENSORS

Electrical conductivity (EC) sensors measure soil's ability to conduct electrical current, which is influenced by soil properties like moisture, salinity, and temperature. While EC sensors do not directly measure SOC, they can provide valuable indirect information that may correlate with SOC in certain conditions. These sensors are highly scalable and can be deployed over large areas, often in combination with other soil sensors, to create soil property maps. EC sensors are commonly used in precision agriculture to manage soil health, irrigation, and crop production. Their low cost and ease of deployment make them attractive for large-scale applications, though their indirect nature limits accuracy for SOC measurement.

INELASTIC NEUTRON SCATTERING

Inelastic Neutron Scattering (INS) Soil Carbon Method uses fast neutrons to non-destructively measure SOC content by detecting inelastic interactions between neutrons and carbon atoms in the soil. This method provides a direct, in situ measurement of SOC without requiring soil sampling or extensive laboratory analysis. INS can scan large areas quickly and repeatedly, offering real-time data on SOC distribution at various depths.

Best in the category

Categories:

Accuracy – How accurate the technology is in measuring soil carbon stocks changes or related parameters.

Scalability – The ease with which the technology can be applied on a larger scale or across various regions and contexts.

Technology Readiness – The level of development and market readiness of the technology.

Cost-effectiveness – The balance between the benefits the technology provides and its associated costs.

Relevance – The significance of the technology in enabling or supporting an effective MRV (Monitoring, Reporting, and Verification) system for Carbon Farming.

The results are based on a questionnaire conducted among FG3.2 members and reflect their subjective statements.

3.3 Vis-NIR as an exemplar soil carbon proximal sensing technology

Basics of Vis-NIR as an exemplar spectroscopy-based technique

Based on the results presented in the *Table*, Vis-NIR spectroscopy appears as the preferred proximal sensing approach, it is thus worth examining further. It relies on the fact that soil constituents—such as minerals, organic matter, and water—absorb and scatter electromagnetic radiation differentially across specific features or wavelength intervals. The visible (Vis; 400–700 nm), near-infrared (NIR; 700–2,500 nm), and mid-infrared (MIR; 2,500–25,000 nm) regions contain diagnostic absorption features that are strongly associated with SOC and other soil properties (Viscarra Rossel et al., 2006).

Among these techniques, Vis-NIR spectroscopy (portable, in situ) is particularly promising for SOC estimation. Absorption features caused by the overtones and combinations of fundamental vibrations of C–H, O–H, and N–H functional groups provide information on organic matter content. Reflectance spectra collected from soil can thus be used to quantitatively predict SOC concentration when combined with appropriate calibration models (Stenberg et al., 2010).

Vis-NIR spectroscopy is rapid, cost-effective, non-destructive, and can estimate multiple soil properties from a single spectral scan. Furthermore, modern portable spectrometers allow for in situ field measurements, making the approach scalable and practical. SOC is among the most reliably predicted properties, which explains the growing use of VIS-NIR in soil monitoring and carbon stock assessments (Stevens et al., 2010).

Scientific principles, calibrations, and stock estimation with Vis-NIR spectroscopy

The predictive power of Vis-NIR spectroscopy rests on establishing statistical relationships between soil reflectance spectra and measured SOC concentrations. This requires robust calibration against laboratory reference data. Calibration models are commonly built using Partial Least Squares Regression (PLSR), which is well-suited for high-dimensional and collinear spectral data (Viscarra Rossel et al., 2006).

In addition, machine learning algorithms are increasingly applied and often outperform linear approaches in heterogeneous soil conditions (Stevens et al., 2010; Sanderman et al., 2020; see more in *Section 4*).

The process of translating a measured spectrum into an SOC prediction involves comparing the reflectance values at multiple wavelengths with the spectral signatures stored in calibration models or spectral libraries. Each wavelength contains information

about chemical bonds, organic matter composition, and moisture content. The model uses these patterns to predict SOC concentration, effectively “reading” the spectral fingerprint of the soil. For illustrative purposes, example spectra for soils with low, medium, and high SOC content could be shown to demonstrate how spectral differences correspond to SOC variation.

The reliability of predictions depends heavily on the availability of spectral libraries: large databases of soil spectra linked to laboratory analyses. These libraries allow for broader model transferability across regions and reduce the need for repeated local calibration (Brown et al., 2006). Preprocessing steps such as baseline correction, smoothing, or normalization are also critical to minimize the impact of noise, soil moisture, soil water content, and measurement conditions (Stenberg et al., 2010).

Figure 2: Vis-NIR proximal sensing stock estimation overview.

In practice, SOC stock estimation requires combining spectroscopic SOC concentration predictions with additional parameters. The SOC stock is calculated as (Grüneberg et al., 2018):

$$SOC_{stock} = SOC_{concentration} \times \text{bulk density} \times \text{depth}$$

Accurate stock assessment, therefore, depends not only on reliable spectral data for SOC concentration but also on precise measurements of bulk density and sampling depth. Bulk density is commonly determined using traditional soil cores, penetrometers, or gamma-ray sensors to account for soil compaction and texture (Soil Copernicus, 2018). For verification and monitoring projects, however, the key parameter is often the **change in SOC stock over time (ΔSOC)** rather than the absolute stock. In such cases, bulk density may partially cancel out if it remains stable, though any temporal or management-induced changes in bulk density require measurement at both time points to avoid bias.

Some modern approaches—particularly in proximal sensing systems or predictive modelling frameworks—aim to reduce the need for direct bulk density measurements by using pedotransfer functions, historical datasets, or sensor-derived proxies. These methods estimate bulk density from soil type, texture, and other measurable soil properties, allowing SOC stock (and potentially Δ SOC) to be inferred even when direct measurements are limited. While this flexibility can substantially reduce fieldwork requirements, it may introduce additional uncertainty that must be managed through careful calibration, validation, and, where possible, periodic direct measurements.

3.4 Building a Vis-NIR spectroscopy-based MRV: Challenges and possible ways forward

While Vis-NIR spectroscopy holds considerable promise, its application within MRV frameworks for carbon farming faces several challenges.

Measurement issues and uncertainties. SOC estimation accuracy is influenced by soil heterogeneity, moisture variability, water content, surface roughness, and instrument-specific factors. Without careful preprocessing, calibration, and validation, these sources of variability introduce substantial uncertainty into predictions (Stenberg et al., 2010). Reported uncertainty levels for SOC estimates derived from proximal sensing remain higher than the <5% error margins typically required for credible carbon market applications ([Soil Copernicus](#), 2018).

Standards and comparability. For Vis-NIR to be trusted in MRV frameworks, standardized protocols are essential. International standards such as [ISO 17184:2014](#) (Soil quality — Determination of carbon and nitrogen by near-infrared spectrometry) and the Standard Operating Procedures of the Soil-Plant Spectral Diagnostics Laboratory ([ICRAF](#)) provide important guidelines for consistency across platforms and laboratories. Nevertheless, there is currently no overarching standard covering proximal sensing technologies as a whole, which complicates the comparability and integration of data across projects.

Spectral databases and sampling strategies. Developing and maintaining robust soil spectral libraries remains a key challenge. Soil diversity, especially across different climatic zones, requires extensive sampling to capture representative variability. *Adaptive sampling strategies*—which iteratively refine sampling locations based on prior measurements, model uncertainty, or spatial heterogeneity—can substantially improve

data representativeness and model accuracy. For instance, adaptive schemes may focus on areas with the highest prediction errors from preliminary models, underrepresented soil types, or regions showing high variability in remotely sensed indices such as NDVI or surface reflectance. Machine learning and geostatistical tools (e.g., kriging variance or active learning algorithms) are increasingly used to guide these designs (Wadoux et al., 2019). By focusing effort where new information is most valuable, adaptive sampling enhances the efficiency, robustness, and transferability of calibration models across regions and conditions (Brown et al., 2006).

Innovation versus standardization. While standardization is essential for comparability and certification, it may risk constraining innovation. There is a tension between establishing technological standards too early and leaving space for methodological innovation (Hamidov et al., 2022). A balanced approach is needed, whereby new technologies are encouraged and tested before rigid standards are imposed (see also Recommendations in *Section 5*).

In short, to enable the use of Vis-NIR within MRV frameworks for carbon farming, three elements are critical: (i) standardized and transparent measurement protocols, (ii) uncertainty reporting in line with market requirements, and (iii) integration of spectroscopy with other methods (e.g., bulk density measurements) to close key data gaps.

3.5 Vis–NIR spectroscopy-based MRV case studies

In recent years, several proximal sensing systems have been developed to operationalize spectroscopy-based soil carbon monitoring for carbon farming and certification. Two prominent examples are SoilCASTOR*, developed by AgroCares, Wageningen University and partners, and Yard Stick PBC*, a U.S.-based start-up. Both are rooted in visible–near infrared (Vis-NIR) spectroscopy, yet they differ in their implementation, calibration strategies, and integration of ancillary measurements, illustrating that there is not yet a single unified approach to spectroscopy-based SOC monitoring.

SoilCASTOR(AgroCares)*

SoilCASTOR represents a comprehensive approach to operationalize spectroscopy-based SOC monitoring at farm scale. It combines field-based NIR spectroscopy (Kok et al., 2024) with satellite imagery, machine learning, and automated calibration to estimate SOC stocks (van der Voort et al., 2023). The approach relies on a large proprietary

spectral database (>20,000 samples) and [optimized sampling designs](#), such as Conditioned Latin Hypercube Sampling, to capture [soil variability efficiently](#), and apply ML methods to quantify uncertainties on measured SOC stocks. While the AgroCares Scanner provides SOC concentration and soil particle density estimates, bulk density can be obtained from pedotransfer functions, digital soil mapping algorithms (as done in SoilCASTOR) or spectral modelling, which is a critical step for stock calculations ([Soil Copernicus](#), 2018). This end-to-end integration—from sensor measurement to stock estimation—demonstrates how a Vis–NIR sensor can be embedded within a modelling and data-fusion framework to deliver reliable, scalable SOC estimates suitable for MRV purposes. Uncertainty at the farm scale is reported to be below 5%, meeting thresholds necessary for MRV systems linked to carbon markets, and results are typically delivered as SOC stocks and CO₂-equivalent per hectare, enabling integration with sustainability schemes.

*Yard Stick PBC**

Yard Stick also employs Vis–NIR spectroscopy but focuses on in-situ, handheld measurements. The probe captures “spectral movies” from the soil profile to depths of up to 45 cm (Gyawali et al., 2025), with a 1 m probe in development. Yard Stick integrates bulk density measurements directly during probing, allowing SOC stocks to be derived without external datasets. A key emphasis of Yard Stick is reducing measurement costs, while providing data traceable through digital dashboards that support auditing and compliance.

Both systems demonstrate how spectroscopy can be deployed in practice but reflect different “philosophies” of MRV design. The main difference lies in how the soil is analysed by the sensor. *Yard Stick* measures soil directly in the ground by inserting the sensor into the profile, capturing SOC concentration and bulk density on site. *SoilCASTOR*, on the other hand, collects soil samples that are then analysed separately in the field and combined with ancillary datasets, such as satellite observations, to produce high-resolution SOC stock maps. Thus, while Yard Stick focuses on direct, field-based measurement, SoilCASTOR emphasizes scalability through sample-based analysis and data integration.

These examples highlight that Vis–NIR spectroscopy has become the cornerstone of proximal sensing for SOC monitoring, but the operational pathways diverge significantly—particularly in how bulk density is handled, the unit of delivered results, and the extent to which SOC estimates rely on direct field measurements versus model-based predictions supported by ancillary data.

**Representatives of SoilCASTOR (via AgroCares) and YardStick PBC are engaged in the work of our FG3.2. While other companies in FG3.2 do not rely on spectroscopy (see FG3.2 Report, table “Market context”, for details), and external companies may also employ spectroscopy-based approaches, these two examples are presented here purely for illustration. This section does not imply that SoilCASTOR or Yard Stick are better or worse than other available solutions, nor does it assess the commercial value of these companies.*

MRV Implications

Because—at the time of writing—the European MRV framework for carbon farming has not yet been implemented, we refer to Verra’s Verified Carbon Standard (VM0042, Improved Agricultural Land Management) ([Verra, 2025](#)) as an example of project-level MRV protocols used in the voluntary carbon market. These protocols require SOC stock estimates with robust uncertainty quantification, transparent methodology, and full auditability. The two presented examples illustrate emerging approaches relevant to SOC monitoring, and their contrasting designs underline the field lacks a unified framework for spectroscopy-based SOC estimation and reporting. Thus, while the existence of multiple methodologies reflects a healthy stage of innovation but also illustrates why broader standardization across proximal sensing technologies and MRV components remains a challenge (Hamidov et al., 2022; [Soil Copernicus](#), 2018).

Moreover, an ongoing discussion within the carbon accounting community, including under the VCS, concerns whether bulk density (BD) measurements are always necessary. Some argue that monitoring SOC change using SOC concentration (%) together with fixed BD assumptions can be scientifically defensible and reduce uncertainty introduced by BD measurements. Others emphasize that assuming constant BD may not capture real changes in soil structure or management impacts and could bias SOC stock change estimates. This debate highlights the need for further harmonization and evidence-based guidance on how BD should be treated within MRV frameworks.

Proximal sensing technologies, including SoilCASTOR and Yard Stick, show potential to meet MRV requirements, but several challenges remain. Key issues include ensuring robust uncertainty quantification, method transparency, and auditability across diverse sensors and calibration approaches. The lack of harmonized standards makes it difficult for any single technology to fully comply with frameworks like the VCS, highlighting the need for standardized protocols, validation procedures, and reporting methods. In this sense, the main problem is that, without standardization, differences between technologies and site-specific calibration needs create uncertainties that limit full MRV compliance. The lack of a harmonized performance evaluation framework is also a key barrier to scalable deployment of proximal sensing technologies from SoilCASTOR, Yard Stick, or others.

In summary, the examples of SoilCASTOR and Yard Stick illustrate both the promise and the current diversity of spectroscopy-based MRV systems. Both deliver actionable SOC data for carbon farming, but through different technical pathways, demonstrating that the sector is still evolving toward harmonized standards and practices. Moreover, both examples highlight the importance of digitalization in carbon farming—not only as a way to lower costs, enhance accuracy, and scale data collection, but also to ensure transparency and auditability. Their approaches demonstrate that the success of spectroscopy-based MRV systems depends not only on technical calibration and uncertainty handling, but also on how easily the technologies can be integrated into farm management workflows. This raises broader questions of technology acceptance, farmer perspectives, and adaptation in real-world contexts, which will be discussed further in *Section 5*.

4. Digital technologies for proximal sensing in carbon monitoring

4.1 Introduction to proximal sensing-related digitalization

Digitalization is a cornerstone of innovation in modern agriculture, particularly in the development of sustainable carbon farming practices. Within the framework of the European CREDIBLE project, digital tools and technologies are positioned as enablers for reducing costs, increasing efficiency, and addressing climate challenges in the agricultural sector. A key regulatory impulse, as emphasized in the [EU Strategic Dialogue \(2024\)](#), identifies digitalization as a lever to drive sustainable practices and achieve climate objectives. In this work, we focus on the monitoring aspects of MRV – for a wider perspective, please see [Technical Guidance Note on Standardizing Digital MRV in Carbon Markets: System Evaluation Criteria and Hotspots Assessment \(2025\)](#).

The private sector is already leading the way, with large agricultural input suppliers investing in digitalization to streamline operations and enhance productivity. At the same time, the farming community is actively adopting digital technologies to modernize their practices and improve efficiency. However, concerns persist about the imbalance in the value chain, with farmers urging for equitable access to the benefits of digital innovation. In the context of carbon farming, digitalization plays a critical role in lowering the costs of monitoring, reporting, and verification (MRV) processes as well as in the simplification and structuring (e.g., automatization) of bureaucracy and documentation, which is essential for carbon certification and monetization. Advanced monitoring solutions, such as mobile and fixed platform proximal sensing systems, modelling, artificial intelligence, and machine learning, are integral to reducing soil sampling costs, making carbon sequestration programs more accessible to farmers.

4.2 Digital ecosystem: from data to decision support

Digital ecosystems play a pivotal role in enabling carbon farming by integrating key components. This section explores how these elements collectively enhance the management and optimization of carbon-related agricultural practices, fostering more informed and efficient decision-making processes in a rapidly evolving digital landscape.

External data sources to complement proximal sensing

Carbon farming relies on diverse and robust data sources to monitor soil health, carbon sequestration, and agricultural practices, in addition to proximal sensing discussed above, which is just one joint in the MRV data pipeline. Key sources include the harmonized Land Use/Cover Area Frame Survey ([LUCAS](#)), national soil monitoring systems, private data providers, and, increasingly, farmer-generated data.

LUCAS, while harmonized across the EU, lacks the detail required for comprehensive carbon farming applications, particularly regarding organic matter data. Member states often supplement LUCAS with their soil monitoring systems, offering more localized and detailed insights. The upcoming EU Soil Health Law will mandate member states to strengthen these systems, ensuring data on carbon sequestration is digitally accessible for use by market operators.

Among these, digital field books and more complete Farm Management Information Systems ([FMIS](#)) have emerged as a vital tool for capturing on-the-ground data directly from farmers. These tools record real-time activities such as crop rotations, fertilizer applications, and soil management practices. Digital field books, in particular, have the potential to guide monitoring efforts by indicating where changes in soil organic carbon (SOC) are expected over time, helping to target proximal sensing and traditional soil sampling more effectively. Supported [by EU regulations](#) (2023), many countries, for instance, Spain or Greece, are actively promoting their use. Farmers can also integrate traditional soil analyses and advanced monitoring systems, such as portable sensors or third-party services to populate their digital records.

Private companies offer additional data through digital platforms and soil monitoring services. However, the reluctance of private actors to share data remains a challenge. New legislation, such as the [Data Act](#), should help to address this by giving users greater control over the data generated by their connected devices.

The increasing reliance on digital field books highlights the need for standardised data collection and sharing practices. By harmonising these efforts and ensuring data is accessible in digital formats, stakeholders can collaborate effectively. This will support accurate measurement and verification of carbon sequestration, fostering trust in the growing carbon certificate market and advancing sustainable agriculture goals across Europe.

Connectivity

Connection plays a critical role in enabling efficient soil -digital- carbon management. To ensure fair access to data, the [Strategic Dialogue report on EU agriculture](#) (2024) emphasizes the need to accelerate investments in digital infrastructure so high-speed internet connectivity can reach all rural areas across Europe. Precision agriculture technology, such as IoT-enabled proximal sensors, drones, artificial intelligence, and satellite imaging, depends on investments in rural digital infrastructure, such as high-speed broadband and increased connectivity. These tools improve crop management and resource efficiency, supporting sustainable agricultural methods. While proper financing for research and development is required to improve data gathering techniques, analytical tools, algorithms, and AI applications for processing complex datasets, incentives within the [CAP](#) (2025) framework could hasten their implementation. Despite the significance of connectivity, carbon farming is less dependent on continuous connectivity than other agricultural sectors due to its unique requirements, which centre on long-term soil carbon dynamics rather than real-time data. However, to fully realise the potential of data-driven soil carbon management and scale carbon farming practices throughout the EU, good connectivity, offline solutions, and a strong data governance system are essential.

The role of Artificial Intelligence in proximal sensing and the digital ecosystem

As in other fields, AI is a potentially transformative technology for carbon farming MRV. A full consideration of AI is outside the scope of this report, so instead, we highlight the key benefits and challenges in relation to measurement technologies such as proximal sensing. Potential benefits of AI include:

- **Automated data analyses** potentially reduce the cost and processing times of large datasets. These can greatly amplify insights for farmers and researchers alike
- There is also very high potential for **efficient use of unstructured agricultural data**, which comes from a multitude of sources. AI can be deployed, for example, on remote sensing images and proximal sensor outputs, to automatically extract relevant features, something that traditional approaches cannot easily achieve.
- Emerging AI technologies, such as **agents**, could be used to automate reporting and verification workflows, saving significant resources.

There are several significant challenges related to data quality, including:

- **Data biases** that significantly influence results. Source, including sampling methods, sensor calibration, and even subjective interpretations of data. Data quality must be ensured.
- **Poor generalization** is a particular problem for scale-dependent MRV systems, which can be at risk of both under- and over-fitting. Rigorous testing on independent datasets must be used to validate performance.
- AI models are sometimes referred to as unexplainable “**black boxes**”. Developing interpretable models and establishing standards for data quality and transparency is critical to ensuring these tools are effective and widely adopted in carbon farming.

Decision support systems (FMIS)

Farm Management Information Systems ([FMIS](#)) are vital tools for supporting sustainable farming, including carbon accounting. These systems present data visually, allowing users to model scenarios and optimize decisions. Two main models exist: specialized tools focused on carbon farming and general FMIS that include carbon sequestration modules. Both leverage analytics and machine learning to improve decision-making, balancing productivity with sustainability. However, interoperability between systems is crucial to avoid data fragmentation.

4.3 Data sharing from farm to region

Effective soil carbon accounting depends on efficient aggregation and exchange of data from the farm to the regional and national levels. Two main approaches to data sharing have emerged: localized, farm-to-farm exchanges and centralized platforms aggregating data from numerous sources. Each offers distinct advantages and challenges.

Localised Data Sharing (Farm-to-Farm) is a collaborative approach that focuses on fostering networks, cooperatives, and advisory relationships within local farming communities. This approach fosters trust among participants and a collective commitment to sustainable land management. However, there are limitations to its scalability, and the lack of standardised formats or a central authority may present challenges to broader applicability.

Centralised data sharing (global-to-local) aggregates farm-level data into larger platforms, offering significant opportunities for large-scale analysis, benchmarking, and policy development. While this approach allows for more comprehensive insights, it

introduces concerns about data ownership, privacy, and misuse, which must be addressed. There is a risk of power imbalances, as farmers may feel disengaged from the systems utilising their data. Nevertheless, the potential for in-depth analysis and the capacity to influence regional or national strategies are significant advantages.

As an example, COOP ([Agri-food Cooperatives of Spain](#)) is involved in a localised data sharing initiative amongst their farms at the same time that it also collaborates with the national centralised data sharing SLEX platform, launched by the agricultural ministry. The first one relies on mutual benefit among farmers, exchanging data to improve their knowledge. The Hub for data collection is the “data cooperative”, which means the local cooperative that, in addition to their traditional activities, now facilitates data exchanges. As it is said, at the same time, National authorities are trying to implement mandatory digital logging of actions on the farm. In its experience, COOP learnt advantages and disadvantages in both formulas, with merged models as more successful.

The issue of data sharing from individual farmers to larger platforms presents a complex scenario, with many potential opportunities and challenges to be considered. Farmers stand to benefit from advanced analytics, benchmarking, and participation in carbon credit markets. However, several obstacles hinder participation:

Lack of clear incentives: Many farmers are hesitant to share data if they do not clearly understand the tangible benefits. Benefits such as improved farm management tools, access to markets, or financial benefits through carbon farming programmes seem distant and complex to farmers who are unfamiliar with the technology. Ownership and privacy concerns: Regulations like the EU’s General Data Protection Regulation ([GDPR](#), 2016) require robust safeguards to protect personal data. Farmers need transparent protocols clarifying ownership and usage rights while distinguishing between personal and non-personal data.

Technological barriers and digital literacy: A lack of familiarity with digital systems among aged European farmers represents a significant challenge to the implementation of electronic data sharing. It is crucial to implement training and user-friendly platforms to overcome these barriers. Involving end users in the tool design process is key to ensuring technology is adopted successfully. Young people also need specialised training to unfold their full potential as digital natives. Training for intermediate/advanced level in Data/AI Literacy will more likely become an important skillset also in agriculture.

Existing regulatory frameworks: Efforts such as the EU Code of Conduct ([COPA-COGECA](#), 2018), the work of the International Agrifood Data Standardisation Committee,

and the [Data Act](#) Initiative provide essential guidance for data governance. These frameworks emphasize fair, transparent, and secure data usage, forming a foundation for effective sharing practices. Cooperatives play a crucial role in data sharing by fostering trust, aggregating member data, and providing training to overcome technological barriers. Their established structures make them effective intermediaries, ensuring data privacy and advocating for farmer-friendly policies. However, their impact depends on broader support, including technological advancements, clear governance frameworks, and tangible farmer benefits.

5. Perspective and social uptake of emerging technologies

5.1 Adoption and acceptance of emerging technologies

Technology adoption and technology acceptance are two closely related terms that are often used to understand and organize socio-cultural change. While technology acceptance primarily aims to improve a target group's understanding of the technology, adaptation focuses on socio-economic framework conditions that are geared towards the motivation and belief in the transformation. At the implementation level, there is a clear distinction between acceptance and adaptation activities. For example, information campaigns or specific training programs are initiated to increase acceptance. To increase adaptation rates to a carbon farming economy, the motivations, incentive mechanisms, and economic framework conditions of farmers must be carefully understood and addressed.

The adoption of proximal sensing technologies for soil carbon MRV among European farmers is influenced by a complex interplay of factors, including economic viability, technological compatibility, and socio-cultural acceptance. Economic considerations are paramount; the initial costs of implementing proximal sensing tools could be a significant barrier (upfront investment costs versus return on investment over time), especially for small-scale farmers. Farmers generally evaluate new technologies based on their potential to enhance productivity, reduce labour, and align with environmental and regulatory standards. Others may be attracted by sheer curiosity or the excitement that technology can provoke in them.

5.2 Technological uptake on the farm

Financial incentives, such as subsidies or cost-sharing programs, have been shown to facilitate technology uptake, as well as shared services (e.g., cooperatives providing access to equipment). The European Union's Common Agricultural Policy ([CAP](#), 2025) provides frameworks that support the integration of innovative technologies through various funding mechanisms. The compatibility of new technologies with existing farming practices also plays a crucial role. Farmers are more inclined to adopt technologies that seamlessly integrate into their current operations without necessitating extensive changes. So, if sensors provide additional benefits for farm management in addition to carbon measurement, such as other parameters of the chemical and physical structure

of the soil, it will be easier to implement. Comprehensive training and extension services are essential to enhance farmers' technical skills and confidence in using new tools.

Quite usual, the farmers hire specific services, especially the ones that require complex knowledge, maybe soil carbon MRV is still within this scope so far. Some usual providers of products and services in agriculture (fertilisers or phytos) are starting to deliver these services; for instance, Syngenta offers TERRASCAN technology that combines gamma ray spectrometry with soil sampling calibration. BAYER also bet on a service based on modelling from remote sensing and on-site sampling. The latter is also the choice of the main providers for carbon farming. Those actors will be in a position to push the technologies, and due to their long-standing relationship with the sector, farmers are more confident in their approaches.

National legislation can boost technology uptake, as it can sometimes force farmers to transform their businesses. However, farmers have the perception that there is already too much regulation on the agri-food sector and way too much administrative work to deal with. Therefore, this type of legislative action should be implemented with sufficient time for them to reflect, understand, and adapt. Otherwise, it may provoke outbursts of anger like those experienced in early 2024 in many European countries. Additionally, policymakers should bear in mind that agricultural economies are based on crop revenues, not climate targets. Carbon farming efforts must balance narrowly speaking to climate/GHG/CO₂ goals and broader but more economically relevant adjacencies like supply chain resilience, soil health, and reduced crop risk. If proximal SOC MRV technologies "only" talk about climate, and not these broader concerns, which are more central to the actual economics of all agricultural systems, they will remain limited to a purist climate science community and will remain insignificant and impactful vs. broadly inspiring transformation. In short, carbon farming efforts, and therefore proximal SOC MRV technologies, must speak directly to the business model of today's actual agricultural economy to have any impact of substance.

Socio-cultural factors, including peer influence and community norms, significantly impact technology adoption. Farmers are more likely to adopt new technologies when they observe successful implementation by their peers. Creating platforms for knowledge exchange and showcasing local success stories can foster a positive attitude towards innovation. Additionally, addressing data privacy concerns is critical, as trust in how data is managed influences farmers' willingness to engage with digital tools. The European Union has recognized the importance of data governance in building such trust, as evidenced by the [Data Governance Act](#) (2022), which aims to enhance data sharing while

ensuring data privacy and security. Trust in the accuracy and reliability of data provided by proximal sensing devices also plays a significant role in their decision-making process.

Farmers are increasingly looking at carbon farming as a way to boost their incomes while improving soil health and reducing emissions. By adapting to practices that capture and store carbon in the soil, they can earn carbon credits, which can then be sold to companies looking to offset their emissions. There are several side benefits related to this:

- Improved soil health: Practices such as cover crops, reduced tillage, and rotational grazing can lead to higher yields over time.
- Lower input costs: Regenerative agriculture reduces dependence on synthetic fertilizers and pesticides.
- Government incentives: Some regions offer subsidies or grants for the adoption of climate-smart agriculture.
- Higher prices: Consumers and businesses are willing to pay more for sustainably grown products.
- Risk Sharing: Long-term investment risks for special crop farmers with perennial crops (e.g., apples, oranges, olives) would be shared and potentially decreased thanks to the revenues that carbon credits should provide.

5.3 A multifaceted approach to boost adaptation

One of the biggest challenges that farmers face in adapting to carbon farming is the lack of awareness about MRV technologies, along with the uncertainty caused by the absence of a standardized methodology. Currently, different carbon markets have their own methodologies, leading to uncertainty for farmers. A globally recognized carbon farming MRV framework would help to build farmer confidence, ensure consistency in credit pricing, and make it more attractive to invest.

Advisory services, offered for instance by cooperatives, state institutions, or specialized consultancies, play a key role in supporting adaptation efforts in carbon farming MRV technologies. Since many farmers lack awareness and technical knowledge, these different advisory services can act as trusted intermediaries to guide them through the complexities of carbon farming. In addition, shared MRV services may reduce individual costs and lower adaptation barriers. For instance, smallholders could reach more or better deals with carbon buyers and therefore get more used to a carbon farming economy.

Access to education and training is vital for the successful adoption of digital technologies in agriculture. Funding mechanisms that provide possibilities to test new technology/machinery on site in cooperation with a research organization lower financial risks, raise job attractiveness for young professionals, and increase the possibility of adaptation efforts among farmers. Especially agricultural pioneers or lead farms should be focused on this kind of program, as they usually provide the willingness and manpower to be able to take the associated risks. Decision makers should carefully weigh the available national and EU-wide funding mechanisms with the specifics of carbon farming technologies in order to foster technology acceptance and boost technology adoption. A multilevel process of discussing and forging appropriate funding schemes is proposed for the uptake of SOC MRV technologies. Raising technology acceptance and motivating farmers to adopt new technologies can be approached in numerous ways. Therefore, it is suggested that research concerning cultural and social aspects of this phenomenon is part of the development of carbon farming legislation. Useful tools, for instance, are frameworks like the adaptive capacity wheel or comparable frameworks for social innovation and change.

In conclusion, enhancing the adoption of proximal sensing technologies for soil carbon monitoring among European farmers requires a multifaceted approach. This approach should encompass economic support, educational initiatives, and the cultivation of a supportive socio-cultural environment, which are discussed within this section.

6. Recommendations for EU policies

Proximal sensing should be integrated with laboratory analysis in EU MRV strategies as a cost-effective, scalable, and accurate tool for monitoring soil organic carbon.

Proximal sensing technologies (e.g., Vis-NIR spectroscopy) provide a cost-effective and scalable measurement method for MRV (Measurement, Reporting, and Verification) of soil organic carbon (SOC), enabling more frequent, yet still accurate monitoring for carbon farming initiatives. Hence, relevant EU legislation (e.g., under delegated acts and implementing acts) should ensure that MRV strategies incorporate proximal sensing technologies alongside laboratory chemical analysis (used for calibration and validation).

The EU should increase funding for proximal sensing R&I to improve accuracy, expand open-access SOC data libraries, and establish harmonized performance evaluation frameworks.

The EU should increase funding for research and innovation in proximal sensing technologies, particularly to improve accuracy, establish open-access SOC data libraries, and develop a harmonized framework for performance evaluation. Currently, different technologies and providers report performance using inconsistent metrics, making direct comparisons difficult. EU-supported efforts could focus on creating standardized protocols and metrics, alongside expanding open-source proximal sensing data libraries (e.g., building on initiatives like ISRIC), to ensure reliable and comparable SOC estimates for MRV applications.

Flexible, good-enough methodological frameworks—rather than overly rigid or delayed ones—are needed to support proximal sensing-based carbon farming projects.

A good-but-not-perfect methodological framework should be prioritized over delayed perfection to avoid stalling progress. Verra VM0042 is an example of a well-developed methodology. However, VM0042 has detailed guidelines on bulk density (BD), which potentially hinder proximal sensing-focused projects. To support carbon farming, a more flexible methodology could be developed to prevent valuable projects from being sidelined due to overly restrictive criteria. When an approach is peer-reviewed and published in a scientific journal, this can be seen as an indicator of the quality of the approach.

EU regulations should enable digitalisation in carbon farming by ensuring data interoperability, GDPR compliance, farmer training, and support for affordable sensing technologies.

Regulatory framework(s) that standardize and support digitalisation in carbon farming should consider large data streams coming from emerging proximal sensing techniques, with the aim to, e.g., ensure data interoperability, clear GDPR-compliant data ownership rules, and fund digital literacy training for farmers. Supporting cooperatives as trusted data intermediaries and incentivizing affordable, automated sensing devices will lower MRV costs and improve accuracy. Such measures will foster farmer trust, equitable access, and scalable adoption of digital tools essential for sustainable carbon sequestration and climate targets.

The EU should foster farmer adoption of proximal sensing-based MRV by providing financial incentives, training, harmonized standards, and linking uptake to clear farm-level benefits.

The EU should aim to foster farmer acceptance and uptake of proximal sensing-based soil carbon MRV by aligning policies with farmers' economic realities and motivations. This requires financial incentives and shared-service models to lower entry costs; training and peer-led demonstrations to build skills and trust; and harmonized MRV standards with clear data governance to reduce uncertainty. Linking these measures to tangible farm benefits—like yield stability, soil health, and market access—will strengthen the sector's transformative capacity for carbon farming.

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